

Increasing Purchase Intention through Reciprocity, Corporate Image and Brand Image: Case of the Executive Tunjungan Plaza Mall Surabaya

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Abstract

The brand image and corporate nature of your product is one of the secrets of business success. The accurate brand image of your product can increase the sales of your product and create a foundation for the success of your company. In view of many employees who want to buy formal, yet trendy, high quality and price in The Executive, this brand identity of a company may be the right option. The principle of reciprocity is a very important component in the literature on consumer interest and is one of the most important steps to achieve competitive advantage. In a build, defined as the consumer behavior, all its consequences can be combined. They have a large store in Tunjungan Plaza Mall to enhance the customer's purchasing intention to support the executive brand image. This research will analyze about: the impact of reciprocity on purchase intention, The impact of reciprocity on corporate image; The reciprocity on brand image; The corporate image impact brand image; The impact of corporate image on purchase intention and the impact of image on purchase intention at The Executive Tunjungan Plaza Mall Surabaya.

Key words: reciprocity, brand images, corporate images, purchase intentions

Introduction

When discussing fashion trends in Indonesia, it is definitely impossible to separate the names of fashion designers and events that took place in here during the growth of fashion trends. Fashion trends are fashions that have been popular for a time, including clothing or jewellery. The word fashion is often used in a positive way, primarily as a synonym for glamour, beauty, and lifestyle or styling that has a tendency to change on occasion. Moreover, fashion trends also represent social and economic status, and these are positions in which visibility is taken into account. The rise of world-famous designers and fashion magazines is increasingly making style or design a lucrative industry within the country.

Fashion trends are driven mostly by fashion designers who create and make clothes. In this case, the word Fashion Industry would be used as an innovative enterprise created and manufactured by fashion designers in the sense of a fashionable apparel or clothing industry. Given the growing trend in the fashion world, people are becoming more aware of their appearance and paying attention to it so that buying activities in the fashion sector are increasing.

Fashion is the kind of items that men and women buy most often. Shopping trends data from the above graph, which began in 2019, shows that men or women are purchasing fashion products. 39.3 percent purchased fashion items and accessories for the general male customers, led by 36.8 percent electronics and 18 percent household appliances. While 55 percent of total female consumers bought fashion items and cosmetics, 41 percent bought health and beauty items.

Brand image is one of the main factors affecting the intentions of consumers in the field of fashion. Since this industry has been reported to be cost-sensitive and low labor standards, it has become a serious social issue in the global market (Cooke and He, 2010). Thus, fashion companies regard CSR as an essential part of their image and sales improvement.

Fashion companies need to be scattered through a wide range of brands with regard to corporate businesses and maximize opportunities (Arrigo, 2013; Lopez and Fan, 2009). The fashion industry should therefore study how perceptions of reciprocity affect company photo, brand image and the buying intention of consumers.

The Management is a company from Indonesia. It is obvious that South East Asian countries like Malaysia and Indonesia have been able to achieve this fashion business. Once it first appeared, male managers looked for its goods in Indonesia. Everyone who works in an office always looks luxury and has always been a favorite of the executive brand.

On the basis of a 2014 survey of the Indonesian Original Brand (IOB), the management managed to transform into a dress that men wanted. Moreover, the brands available in several centers do not prevent contemporary fashion inventions by the time. The Management has created fashion items that are not less suitable for women. In Indonesian malls, this company also trades shoes, bags and wallets for managers.

Revenue from the Executive is about 2 million. So for men and women approximately one million. Sales are more or less the same, so that we can't protect anything else. For a month we sold approximately 200,000 parts. If it's about 2.4 million for one year, it means growth. For men alone, the highest (shirts) are about 400,000, since 40 percent of men's items compensate that top.

Regardless of the company, consumers base their purchasing decisions on product or service reciprocity. Therefore, it is critical that we know how to best emphasize the reciprocity of business. The greater the reciprocity, the greater the consumer's intent to purchase the product. For The Executive to increase purchases, reciprocity is therefore necessary.

The subject in this research is The Executive Tunjungan Plaza Mall Surabaya, because The Executive Tunjungan Plaza Mall Surabaya is the biggest store that opened in Surabaya. The Executive has competitive rates to compete with another company. Consumers can be drawn to the store at worthwhile prices.

The brand image and corporate nature of your product is one of the secrets of business success. The accurate brand image of your product can increase the sales of your product and create a foundation for the success of your company. In view of many employees who want to buy formal, yet trendy, high quality and price in The Executive, this brand identity of a company may be the right option.

The principle of reciprocity is a very important component in the literature on consumer interest and is one of the most important steps to achieve competitive advantage. In a build, defined as the consumer behavior, all its consequences can be combined. They have a large store in Tunjungan Plaza Mall to enhance the customer's purchasing intention to support the executive brand image.

Research Questions

This research will analyze about:

1. Does reciprocity impact purchase intention at The Executive Tunjungan Plaza Mall Surabaya?
2. Does reciprocity impact corporate image at The Executive Tunjungan Plaza Mall Surabaya?
3. Does reciprocity impact brand image at The Executive Tunjungan Plaza Mall Surabaya?
4. Does corporate image impact brand image at The Executive Tunjungan Plaza Mall Surabaya?
5. Does corporate image impact purchase intention at The Executive Tunjungan Plaza Mall Surabaya?
6. Does brand image impact purchase intention at The Executive Tunjungan Plaza Mall Surabaya?

Hypothesis Development

Relationship Between Reciprocity And Purchase Intention

The course of an activity evolves through interactive dialog through the acquisition of information. This two-way dialog can help firms to learn from a customer or group (Sawhney et al . 2015). The wealth of an interaction grows because the virtual community of customers helps companies open themselves to social science in addition to the knowledge of customers. Fader & Winner (2012) states that content (ultrasound) generated by users is being developed. Ultrasound not only helps advertisers encourage one-way, but also communicate with brands and consumers in two ways. The interaction between musicians and fans is also influencing one of the factors of the strength, namely reciprocity. The shared behavior and acts of artists are reflected by fans understood and valued. But the fans remembered and

helped the singer, this always happened. In this context, reciprocity is not necessary if there is no successful interaction, which may help and promote a sense of reciprocity with a higher degree of interaction (Daellenbach et al. 2014). The hypothesis to be evaluated in the following research are based on these studies:

H1 : Reciprocity give impact on purchase intention.

Relationships between Reciprocity And Corporate Image

According to Veljkovic (2011), Keller's (2003) theory that suggests the dimensions of corporate image and reciprocity relationships can be shown as follows. Corporate names or brands can draw large customers together with a high level of marketing innovations. The company identity is evident in the workers' attributes, such as customer relations. The identity of the company can be found in the organization's principles and services which do not relate to the goods sold, such as social welfare, environmental conservation. The identity of the company can be reflected in the form of views or decisions concerning the company and in its attitude of faith with respect to the company that is qualified to market goods and offer its services and in the like level and value of its clients.

H2 : Reciprocity give impact on corporate image.

Relationships between Reciprocity And Brand Image

No work in the field of relationship marketing has so far been undertaken on the role of brand identity as a moderating influence on consumer loyalty. This work will also mask this vulnerability. The research followed the model used by Hsieh & Li (2018) to view brand identity as a moderating variable, which looked at the effects of brand image public reciprocity as a moderating variable in Taiwanese insurance firms. Results from research by Hsieh & Li (2018) show that brand images are shown to moderate consumer loyalty impacts on PRP. Consumers with a positive brand identity tend to be more faithful to the product, and consumers with a poor brand image appear to be faithful to the product. Hanzaeen & Farsani (2011) have also published related work. They would like to learn how brand identity reduces the impact of perceived PPRs on LG model electronics' market loyalty. The findings of this analysis find that brand identity has already been shown to serve as a moderating effect on PPR on customer loyalty. The following hypotheses is therefore proposed by this research:

H3 : Reciprocity give impact on brand image.

Relationship Between Corporate Image And Brand Image

Many previous studies have shown that the effect of company advertising on brand images is important. In fact, Write. J (2018) at Mudambi et al . (1997) proved that brand branding is an relevant precedent. Hyun and Kim (2011) find that Corporate Branding mediates brand recognition and brand recognition in marketing combination activities. Such previous research have clearly shown that client photos add to the brand's image. This presumption will boost the public identity of CSR initiatives and have an important impact on the market value with a stronger corporate picture. Their public identity is valued by businesses as it has a positive impact on promotions and business accomplishments; Lee and Kotler 2011; Brown

and Dacin, 1997 Sen and Bhattacharya, 2001). Many experiments have found that company and advertising identities have a significant effect on success factors, for example buying intentions. The company image has an effect on consumer buying intentions and reinforces trust in corporate communication according to Lee. J(2018), Yoon et al . (1993). Bloom and Gundlach (2001) also found that the image of a company influences buying intent either directly or indirectly. Francis et al . (2010).

H4 : Corporate Image give impact on brand image.

Relationship Between Corporate Image And Purchase Intention

KurniaSih (2012) 's analysis "Effect of price and quality of service on consumer loyalty by satisfaction variables" (Astra Motor Siliwangi Semarang, study at AHASS 0002 workshop) further confirms this report, which is an significant corporate picture of transactions again. This shows that good standard of service allows consumers to continue the company. This is more likely that consumers who are disillusioned will not buy potential goods. To businesses, customer delivery may be a powerful tool. Results of Hellier et al (2003) analysis. Srivastava and Sharma (2013) have also verified this study, which has shown service efficiency.

H5 : Corporate image give impact on purchase intention.

Relationship Between Brand Image And Purchase Intention

In Sugiharti (2012) Zeithml and Bitner note that consumers may be affected by consumer imaging 's interpretation of products and/or services offered. The hypothesis indicates that, with respect to lifestyle and social status, the markers in the customer photographs will affect people's desire to purchase a product. So the customer identity is one of the considerations that consumers weigh when choosing the product they want to fulfill their requirements. Fahrian et al(2013), Rachman et al(2014) and Jotopurnomo et al(2014) affirm work findings that have a direct impact on the value in sales.

H6 : Brand image give impact on purchase intention.

Research Framework

After the report, the reciprocity and the plan to buy from the management includes. Accorporate identity and brand value are determined by reciprocity and purchasing intention in the management process, this model shows that reciprocity and purchasing intention is deciding the organizational reputation and image. First and foremost. If the client thinks of the management, it will create an image of the company and brand. The reciprocity and purchase intent impacts from this consumer. Finally, the customer-executive relationship will be established. The role of customer self mediation in the relationship between brand identity, corporate image and potential buying intentions is explored in this report. The hypothesis suggests that mutual reciprocity not only strengthens future purchasing intentions, but also offers an alternate path that integrates brand identity with corporate awareness and future buying intentions. Management believes that businesses can boost their efficiency in maintaining their current clients by leveraging the informal reciprocity of retailers in accordance with business relationships.

RESEARCH METHOD

Research Design

This study used the assumption that objects were identified. This work was developed in a sample format and was specifically dependent on the data collection and analysis. The data used were primary data in which the data were collected from the respondents directly. Researchers would demonstrate in this analysis that there was any impact on corporate image and brand image through reciprocity and purchase intentions. Quantitative research was used in this study. The exploratory research design would be used for this particular study at the beginning, in order to gather data for a deeper understanding of the problem involved.

The operational definitions of each variable are as follows in this study:

Reciprocity Perceptions (RP)

Reciprocity measures the distance and social trust of the clients are the operating definition used in this research for perceptions of reciprocity. The customer's confidence level and the close social distance from the employee can bring hope of reciprocity. In Luigino(2008), two factors have seen to have a major effect on the reciprocity, according to Zahidah (2015). There are two of them:

1. Contact and communication exists between one person and another in two ways, which are between staff and customers.
2. Customers benefit from being a trendsetter, since they use the company's products as a reward.

Purchase Intention (PI)

The intention to buy is described as the possibility for consumers to buy products offered by the store, the possibility for consumers to consider buying products offered by the store, the possibility for consumers to propose this product to others and the possibility for consumers to buy the product. The metrics used were derived from the following: In & Kang in Tariq et al . (2013), which was :

1. Expressly buy products.
Customers will buy product whenever they want or buy whatever goods are discount.
2. Thinking of buying products in the future .
Customer decided to buy product in this store when there is a new arrival.
3. Buying certain products in the future may not be in a hurry to decide to shop for a long time.
Customers will buy the product in this store when they need something.

Corporate Image (CI)

The organizational definition used for corporate image in this research is a general summary of a business identified to customers on the basis of general knowledge circulated within the community, or the perception of the behavior of a business by the public. What can be measured from: indicators that, according to Mayer in Palupi, 2015, affect the image of the company are:

1. Products given to consumers are good.
2. Customers are interested with the products.
3. Customers are satisfied with the overall appearance and feel of the product.

Brand Image (BI)

Brand Image is an idea or definition of a brand when customers hear feelings about a brand. Additionally, if anyone thinks that The Executive Goods don't ignore, it will always help us remember the brand in the consumer's mind. The measure brand image indicators as per Jin et al . , 2012) are as follows:

1. This retail brand has a trendy image.
2. This retail brand has a reputation for quality.
3. This retail brand is already well known.

In this study measurement of variables used a Likert scale of five points. Likert scale is a psychometric scale that is commonly used in questionnaires, and is the most widely used scale in survey research. Likert scale is widely used to measure one's social phenomena attitudes, perceptions and perceptions (Sugiyono, 2017:158).

Type and Source of the Data

A quantitative analysis is used in this study. Quantitative data are numerically measured data (Kuncoro, 2013: 124). Numerical scale or number. This study data uses numbers or numerics for the presentation of data. The primary data sources in this study are because they come from interviewees. In this study , the data source is data directly obtained from respondents. These data have also been directly collected and analyzed from the previous data. Customers and users of The Executive, Surabaya participated in this study.

Tools and Data Collection Methods

A questionnaire provided directly to respondents is the method used to collect data in this report. Questionnaires are techniques for collecting data to answer questions from respondents (Sugiyono, 2014: 199). The data collection method in this study is a survey, specifically by providing questionnaires in writing to the participants. The respondents, namely the executive customers, will answer these questions.

Population, Sample, and Sampling Techniques

Population, Sample and Sampling Technique

People are all classes (objects or subjects) with unique properties selected to test and then draw conclusions (Sugiyono, 2014: 115). Population is a whole. The sample for this research is all who use the product.

The sample is part of the population number and features (Sugiyono, 2004: 116). The sample used for this study was 161 respondents using the executive product. In order to eliminate errors and invalidity of the questionnaire, the number of respondents is 161. A survey of 100–200 people (2006: 605) is adequate to represent a study, so this study employs a survey of 161 respondents, according to Hair, Babin, Anderson and Tatham.

The sampling technique used is non-probability purposive sampling which means that sampling is done randomly (Soewadji, 2012: 140). Where the sample characteristics that have been determined in this study are as follows:

1. Age $\geq$ 17 years (that age is considered to have the ability to make choices).
2. Have used The Executive's product for at least the last 1 year.
3. Live in Surabaya.

3.6. Technical Data Analysis

Structural equation modeling (SEM) is the data analysis methodology used in this particular study. SEM is a statistical technique according to Yamin and Kurniawan (2009), which can also directly assess the relationship model between the latent building and its indicators. The computational method used in the analysis using the SmartPLS 3.0 Software is the Partial Least Square (PLS). PLS-SEM is similar both conceptually and functionally to a multiple regression analysis. The key goal is the maximisation of the variance described in the dependent design and the measurement of data quality based on the measuring model. Here is the explanation for the SmartPLS model fit assessment: The hypothesis exams determine the pattern of structural relations between variables. Hypothesis evaluations can be calculated in two ways: p-value and T-value. When the p-value is 0.05 for each of two variables, the relation between two is essential and the hypothesis is accepted. Meanwhile, with a T-value of $< 1.96 >$ the relationship between two variables is meaningful and hypotheses accepted.

Characteristic of Respondents

To collect research samples, this study uses Google Form as a tool. To be able to fill out the questionnaire, the respondent must meet the requirements. The requirements are at least 17 years old, lived in Surabaya, and have used The Executive in the past one year. The questionnaire was

distributed via Line, What’s app, and also Instagram. Then filled in by 171 respondents and found 161 respondents who qualified to meet the requirements. The non-qualified answers will be removed and excluded from research. Table 4.1 below is a summary of the characteristics of respondents with the majority of the respondents’ age are 17-23 years old, female and student or college student.

Data Analysis

In this study the effect is measured by partial least square (PLS) on reciprocity perceptions, corporate image, and brand image on purchase intention. There are four variables in this research that have been used:

- (1) Reciprocity Perceptions → RP (RP1, RP2, RP3, RP4)
- (2) Purchase Intention → PI (PI1, PI2)
- (3) Corporate Image → CI (CI1, CI2, CI3, CI4)
- (4) Brand Image → BI (BI1, BI2, BI3)

The model for research is shown below :

Outer Model Evaluation (Measurement)

The goal of the outer model analysis is to gain a better understanding of the relationship between the variable layout and the indicator by examining the convergent validity, the composite's discriminating validity and reliability.

Convergent Validity

Convergent validity is the construction calculation should have a positive correlation with the other alternative construct (Hair et al., 2014:119). The convergent validity analysis can be calculated by looking at external loading with the 0.70 cutoff to validate the data. Table 4.7 includes the outer load data for each variable indicator and each indicator must meet the requirements in this research with the 0.70 cut off. It indicates that the predictor and its attribute match very well.

**Table 4.7
Outer Loading**

Variable	Indicator	Factor Loading	Cut Off	Output
RP	RP1	0.724	0.700	Valid
	RP2	0.808	0.700	Valid
	RP3	0.813	0.700	Valid
	RP4	0.844	0.700	Valid
PI	PI1	0.929	0.700	Valid
	PI2	0.877	0.700	Valid
CI	CI1	0.821	0.700	Valid
	CI2	0.805	0.700	Valid
	CI3	0.795	0.700	Valid
	CI4	0.712	0.700	Valid
BI	BI1	0.783	0.700	Valid
	BI2	0.927	0.700	Valid
	BI3	0.880	0.700	Valid

The Average Variance Extracted (AVE) evaluation is another method for calculating convergent validity with the 0.50 cut off. Table 4.8 shows appropriateness of the AVE value for this research.

**Table 4.8
Average Variance Extracted (AVE)**

Variable	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)	Cut Off	Result
RP	0.637	0,500	Valid
PI	0.816	0,500	Valid
CI	0.615	0,500	Valid
BI	0.748	0,500	Valid

Discriminant Validity

Discriminatory validity differs from the other building by empirical standards (Hair et al., 2014:121). The convergent validity analysis can be calculated by looking at the cross-loading of each indicator marked bold, and the bold number from the same horizontal line must be higher than any other attribute. It can be seen from Table 4.9, that each indicator 's cross load is higher than any other variable. This data shows the indicator for each variable is distinct

**Table 4.9
Cross Loading Discriminant Validity**

	BI	CI	PI	RP
BI1	0.783	0.576	0.386	0.484
BI2	0.926	0.553	0.482	0.527
BI3	0.879	0.486	0.500	0.486
CI1	0.460	0.820	0.399	0.429
CI2	0.609	0.804	0.418	0.469
CI3	0.494	0.795	0.345	0.412
CI4	0.358	0.712	0.372	0.427
PI1	0.504	0.503	0.928	0.567
PI2	0.446	0.368	0.877	0.405
RP1	0.481	0.412	0.417	0.724
RP2	0.462	0.490	0.405	0.808

The Average Variance Extracted in Root Squares (AVE) is another way of calculating the discriminant validity. Increased correlation between the latent structure should be given to the square root AVE (Hair et al . 2014). Table 4.10 below shows the product of square root AVE. Due to the measurements of Square Root AVE in Table 4.10, the overall indicators for all variables produce AVE root values higher than those for correlation in other variables. These data illustrate the strong racial validity of the framework of this study.

**Table 4.10
Root AVE Square**

	RP	PI	CI	BI
RP		0.316	0.555	0.336
PI				
CI		0.163		0.435
BI		0.244		

Composite Reliability

By examining Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability, the composite reliability assessment provides an estimate of reliability based on the correlation between indicator variables. The alpha and composite reliability parameters of Cronbach in order to ensure precision of the data are measured by the cutoff = 0,70 for each component. The alpha and composite reliability evaluation in all Cronbach's Table 4.11, indicates that all the component has a value from 0.738 to 0.811, indicating that all the variables are reliable and stable.

Table 4.11

Cronbach's Alpha and Composite of Reliability

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite of Reliability
RP	0.828	0.875
PI	0.771	0.898
CI	0.791	0.864
BI	0.828	0.898

Inner Structural Model Evaluation

The internal model explained the latent variable 's relation. The estimation of the internal model can be determined with the help of R-square, F-square significance, statistical importance, the direction coefficient impact dimension and the testing of hypotheses.

R-Square (R2)

The Determination Coefficient (R2) is used to determine the endogenous variables capability to explain the diversity of exogenous variables, that is, the exogenous variables' contribution to endogenous variables. Table 4.12 shows that the reciprocity perceptions variable R-square value amounts to 0.560 or 56.0%. In addition words Reciprocity Perceptions, brand image and corporate image contributions to purchase intention can be explained through quality variable of 56.0%, while the remainder of 44.0% is added by other variables not listed in this study.

**Table 4.12
Value of R-Square**

	R Square	R Square Adjusted
RP	0.560	0.551

F-square (F2)

In addition , in order to consider the effects of latent variables on positive simulations, the PLS model is often tested by looking at the F-square value (effect size). If F-square value is 0.35, medium if 0.15, and small if 0.02, latent variables have a strong impact.

The results on Table 4.13 show that the effect size value (F2) of the purchase intention has a medium impact on reciprocity perception, but brand image and purchase intention have large impact on reciprocity perceptions .

**Table 4.13
Check Analysis of F-Square Impact Size**

Independent Variable	Dependent Variable
	PI
BI	0.051
CI	0.245
RP	0.445

Path Coefficient

Path coefficient is the estimated path relationship between -1 and +1 in the structural model. Estimated track coefficients close to +1 show a strong relationship with the track. If the path coefficient near the -1 means the path is negative and the coefficient near the 0 shows that the relationship is weaker (Hair et al., 2014). The following explanations are shown in Table 4.15, which shows that the path coefficient is from 0.163 to 0.555 :

1. Purchase intention has positive path coefficient of 0.244. This shows that if Purchase intention variable increase, then brand image variable also increased by 24.4%.
2. Brand image has positive path coefficient of 0.435. This shows that if brand image variable increase, then corporate image variable increase by 43.5%.
3. Purchase intention has positive path coefficient of 0.163. This shows that if purchase intention variable increase, then corporate image variable also increased by 16.3%.
4. Brand image variable has positive path coefficient of 0.336. This shows that if brand image variable increase, then reciprocity perceptions variable increase by 33.6%.
5. Corporate image variable has positive path coefficient of 0.555. This shows that if corporate image variable increase, then reciprocity perceptions variable also increased by 55.5%.
6. Purchase intention has positive path coefficient of 0.316. This shows that if purchase intention variable increase, then reciprocity perceptions variable increase by 31.6%.

**Table 4.15
Coefficient of Path**

	RP	Relationship
BIPI	0.244	Positive
CIBI	0.435	Positive
CIPI	0.163	Positive
RPBI	0.336	Positive
RPCI	0.555	Positive
RPPI	0.316	Positive

Testing of Hypotheses

The aim of hypothesis testing is to determine the hypothesis of the research in chapter 2. The hypothesis criteria are T-statistical as long as 1.96 and P-values as long as 0.005. The hypothesis check results for the analysis sample are shown in Table 4.16 below:

**Table 4.16
Testing of Hypotheses**

Hypothesis	Path	T Statistics	P Values	Result
H1	BI -> PI	2.194	0.0287	Accepted
H2	CI -> BI	4.845	0.0000	Accepted
H3	CI > PI	1.586	0.1133	Rejected
H4	RP -> BI	4.002	0.0001	Accepted
H5	RP -> CI	8.212	0.0000	Accepted
H6	RP -> PI	3.232	0.0013	Accepted

The explanation of the research hypothesis given in Table 4.16 can be seen as follows:

1. Hypothesis 1 (Brand image has significant impact on purchase intention). Based on the test result in the table 4.16, it can be concluded that the T-statistics value is 2.194 with P-value of 0.0287. This has exceeded the minimum requirements of both T-statistics and P-value, meaning that brand image has significant impact on purchase intention of The Executive, thus it can be interpreted that the better of brand image tends to increase purchase intention to The Executive. Therefore, hypothesis 1 is accepted.

2. Hypothesis 2 (corporate image has significant impact on brand image). Based on the test result in the table 4.16, it can be concluded that the T-statistics value is 4.845 with P-value of 0.0000. This has exceeded the minimum requirements of both T-statistics and P-value, meaning that corporate image has significant impact on brand image of The Executive, thus it can be interpreted that the better of corporate image tends to increase brand image to The Executive. Therefore, hypothesis 2 is accepted.

3. Hypothesis 3 (Corporate image has significant impact on purchase intention). Based on the test result in the Table 4.16, it can be concluded that the T-statistics value is 1.586 with P-value of 0.1133. It does not fulfill the T-statistics minimum requirement which is greater than 1.96 and P-value minimum requirement which is below than 0.005. Therefore, hypothesis 3 is rejected.

4. Hypothesis 4 (Reciprocity perceptions has significant impact on brand image). Based on the test result in the Table 4.16, it can be concluded that the T-statistics value is 4.002 with P-value of 0.0001. It fulfill the T-statistics minimum requirement which is greater than 1.96 and P-value minimum requirement which is below than 0.005. Therefore, hypothesis 4 is accepted .

5. Hypothesis 5 Reciprocity perceptions has significant impact on corporate image). Based on the test result in the Table 4.16, it can be concluded that the T-statistics value is 8.212 with P-value of 0.0000. It fulfill the T-statistics minimum requirement which is greater than 1.96 and P-value minimum requirement which is below than 0.005. Therefore, hypothesis 5 is accepted.

6. Hypothesis 6 (Reciprocity perceptions has significant impact on purchase intention).Based on the test result in the table 4.16, it can be concluded that the T-statistics value is 3.232 with P-value of 0.0013. This has exceeded the minimum requirements of both T-statistics and P-value, meaning that reciprocity perceptions has significant impact on purchase intention of The Executive, thus it can be interpreted that the better of reciprocity perceptions tends to increase purchase Intention to The Executive. Therefore, hypothesis 6 is accepted.

Discussion

The Impact of Reciprocity Perceptions on Purchase Intention

Based on the result of hypothesis testing, Reciprocity perceptions has significantly impact on purchase intention at The Executive. This can be proven that positive customer's assessment of high product reciprocity of brand will cause high purchase intention to the product. Descriptive statistics of the reciprocity perceptions variable have a mean value of 3.87. The average value proves that most respondents agreed to the measurement of the reciprocity perceptions variable that the costs they incur are in accordance with the quality of The Executive products.If consumers buy The Executive Product, The Executive products give the worth quality of product.

The results of this research are consistent with research conducted by Sawhney et al., 2015 which states that the customers helps companies to open up to social science in addition to knowledge from customers (individual customer knowledge). It is important for organizations to be able to build strong reciprocity perceptions to the consumers, because reciprocity perceptions will be associated with the future of the company. The level of reciprocity perceptions of The Executive is good, supported also by discounts and promotions conducted by The Executive, making The Executive well known in the minds of consumers.

In this research, the reciprocity perception by most of the respondents are great, and resulting in customer. This result is in accordance with the research's result from (Daellenbach et al. 2014).which prove that reciprocity perception has direct significant positive impact on customer purchase intention; and Fader & Winner (2012) which confirm that customer reciprocity perception significantly influence customer purchase intention on shopping environment.

The Impact of Corporate Image and Brand Image

Based on the results of testing the hypothesis in this research indicate that corporate image has a positive and significant effect on brand image. These findings can be explained that a positive consumer assessment of a good product image on a brand will create high corporate image also in the minds of consumers towards a product brand. Descriptive statistics of the brand image variable have a mean value of 4.08. The average value proves that most respondents agreed to the measurement of the Brand Image variable.

This result is in accordance with the research's result from Write. J (2018) at Mudambi et al . (1997) which indicates that corporate image is positively related to brand image; and also from research conducted by Hyun and Kim (2011) which indicate that corporate image has significant impact on customer brand image. From

this result, it can be concluded that corporate image not just affecting purchase intention, but also affecting the brand image. This shows the importance of maintaining image, meaning that they should maintain to monitor the image of their brand, and keep improve and check the development.

The results of this study are consistent with research conducted by Kotler (2011) Companies are interested in their corporate image because it positively influences marketing activities and company. Which ultimately consumers will feel satisfied with what is offered by The Executive, thus affecting brand image for The Executive products. In other words, the results of this study are in accordance with research conducted by Du et al (2010) that found that a company's image either directly or indirectly influences brand image positively.

The Impact of Reciprocity Perceptions on Corporate Image And Brand Image

The results of testing the third hypothesis in this research indicate that reciprocity perceptions has a positive and significant impact on corporate image and brand image. These findings explain that customer who already have a good quality perception of a product, will cause remember to the product. Descriptive statistics of the variable corporate image and brand image has a mean value of 4.01 and 4.08. The average value proves that most respondents agreed with the measurement of the variables. While customer's reciprocity perceptions was seen to have a significant impact on brand image, the researchers found that a high level of customer reciprocity perceptions still does not create high image in the brand. In other words, there were other variables that have increased image in the brand. The end result of the average brand image still indicates that average respondents respond that think the respondents rely on The Executive reciprocity, making customers feel comfortable with The Executive.

The results of this study are consistent with research conducted by Zeithml and Bitner in Sugiharti (2012) state that consumers' perceptions of goods or services sold can be influenced by Consumer Imagery. Referring to the theory, it can be concluded that the indicators contained in the Consumer Image include lifestyle and social status can influence the interest of individuals to make a purchase of a product. The finding in this research is consistent with the research findings from Fahrian et al(2013), Rachman et al(2014) and Jotopurnomo et al(2014), which confirm the positive effect of reciprocity perceptions on corporate image. This means that retailers like The Executive need to please the customer to build image in the brand.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTION

This research explores the effect of reciprocity, brand images and corporate images in the purchase intentions of The Executive. The results are derived from the hypothesis research results and the discussion in the last chapter. Based on the result of research analysis and discussion in accordance with the purpose of the research, the conclusion can be drawn as follows:

First, The Executive, which means that perceptions of reciprocity strongly affect the purchase intention, decides the buyer. Reciprocity is positive and significant. Customers can recognize and remember a brand more effectively and increase purchase intention. More reciprocity is shown. Second, The Executive's reciprocity perception has a positive impact on the corporate image. Further, it means in order to raise the corporate image by consumer that The Executive gather more event, The Executive should increase the corporate image, it can be either with joint event or bazaar. Third, reciprocity perceptions positively and significantly influence brand image on The Executive, which means good assessment or perception of product in satisfying customer's needs will able to increase brand image. This shows that the role brand image is said to be important. Fourth, Corporate image positively and significantly influence brand image on The Executive, which means good assessment or perception of corporate image influences consumer purchase and strengthens their trust in company's image either directly or indirectly influences brand image. Fifth, Corporate image affects purchase intention positively and significantly on The Executive, which means that corporate image can be used to encourage customers to increase The Executive's purchase intention. Therefore, the higher corporate image that The Executive has also means that it would eventually affected purchase intention to The Executive indirectly through the purchase intention of the consumer itself. Sixth, Brand image positively and significantly influence purchase intention on The Executive, which mean brand image has a strong effect on consumer needs to make the buyer decision. It means that having brand image are important in order to create customers purchase intention towards The Executive.

One of the limitations of this research is the object too general. The goal is to ensure that all executive products are generated without relying on one type. And this study differs independently from the particular case of the individual consumer. Often a brand image goal can shift when other incentives such as advertising and discount affect it.

The researcher makes a number of suggestions and guidelines based on the following hypothesis which must be taken into consideration: In potential studies, the study of a particular commodity form is proposed The Executive Report for further research, which may become more comprehensive and precise. In comparison to other factors and metrics, for example the real actions of respondents purchasing repurchases and word of mouth will also be included. First, on the basis of research results that perceptions of reciprocity have a favorable and important effect on the purpose of purchasing from the executive, it is recommended to try to work in favor of the executive by the use of a variety of goods in customers and prospects. Innovative and informative marketing advertising such as Instagram and Youtube must be maintained by management, truthful information must be given, product specifications fulfilled, the monthly open air balloon at Indonesian centers must be maintained and public activities organized. Second, the findings show that the corporate image and the brand image have a positive and significant influence on the executive. In order for it to improve its role and make a difference with other well-known and more specialized and exclusive retail brands, the business must retain a strong mark and improve its clothes production. Third, on the basis of the

results from the report, which found that the brand image has a significant and important effect on the Executive's purchasing decision, it recommended that the company remain conscious of the consistency and the production of new ideas, and employ trustworthy people to improve the quality of goods and services and encourage loyalty to others. Fourth, in order to gain wide variety business to reach any sector of the industry from low-class to high-class and to do it every generation or years, The executive should be recommended to continue to be creative and produce new products.

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